

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3a*

R	R' (m.p., °C)							
	H	<i>p</i> -MeO	<i>p</i> -EtO	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Me	<i>m</i> -Me	<i>p</i> -Me
Compounds 2								
Phenyl	220 ^a	196 ^o	206 ^o	199 ^o	204 ^o	218 ^c	224 ^o	212 ^b
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	204 ^d	189 ^d	193 ^d	193 ^d	196 ^d	225 ^d	221 ^d	196 ^d
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	182 ^b	185 ^b	189 ^a	209 ^a	194 ^b	177 ^b	181 ^b	171 ^b
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	203 ^b	186 ^a	192 ^b	214 ^a	199 ^b	192 ^a	189 ^a	202 ^a
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	218 ^d	204 ^d	203 ^d	197 ^d	206 ^d	211 ^d	171 ^d	194 ^d
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	202 ^d	195 ^d	188 ^d	197 ^d	193 ^d	225 ^d	221 ^d	206 ^d
2'-Pyridyl	254 ^b	233 ^b	236 ^b	229 ^b	242 ^b	244 ^b	251 ^b	241 ^b
Compounds 3a								
Phenyl	159 ^a	119 ^a	146 ^a	147 ^a	154 ^a	125 ^a	145 ^a	151 ^a
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	185 ^o	127 ^e	113 ^e	126 ^e	157 ^e	133 ^e	140 ^e	154 ^e
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	166 ^e	131 ^e	137 ^e	141 ^e	132 ^e	139 ^e	147 ^e	142 ^e
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	113 ^e	109 ^e	184 ^e	182 ^e	192 ^e	159 ^e	147 ^e	181 ^e
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	181 ^e	176 ^e	168 ^e	192 ^e	185 ^e	171 ^e	167 ^e	178 ^e
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	176 ^a	167 ^a	162 ^a	164 ^a	180 ^a	155 ^a	171 ^a	177 ^a
2'-Pyridyl	240 ^a	172 ^a	130 ^a	112 ^a	149 ^a	110 ^a	140 ^a	127 ^a

*All compounds gave satisfactory nitrogen analysis and were obtained in 60-75% yields. Recrystallised from ^aethanol, ^bmethanol, ^cAcOH, ^daqueous AcOH, and ^eaqueous ethanol.

thiazol-4'-yl)phenyl-*N*^a-phenylthiocarbamide (0.01 mol, 4.0 g), chloroacetic acid (0.012 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.012 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 5 h, during which it gave a clear solution. After cooling, the solution was poured into cold water. The solid was filtered and washed with water. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 159° (Found: C, 64.79; H, 4.13; N, 12.58; S, 14.59. C₂₄H₁₈N₄OS₂ requires C, 65.16; H, 4.07; N, 12.67; S, 14.48%); ν_{max} 1670 (tert. amide), 1610 (imino), 3220 (NH

stretching), 1570 cm⁻¹ (NH bending) and characteristic absorptions of thiazole nucleus; δ (CDCl₃) 3.7 (2H, s, S—CH₂—C=O), 7.28-8.54 (15H, m, Ar) and 9.4 (1H, s, NH); *m/e* 442 (M⁺).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.S.R.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for award of a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. R. A. MANE and D. B. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, 22, 81.
2. R. A. MANE and D. B. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, 22, 690.
3. G. R. NEWKONE and A. NAYAK, *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1979, 25, 83.
4. V. H. PATIL and D. B. INGLE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 1000.
5. T. E. ACHARYA, P. N. DHAL and J. VIHAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1204.

Synthesis of Biflavonoids. Part-II, Oxidative Coupling of Phenolic Ketones with FeCl₃-DMF: Proof for Inter-flavonyl Linkage

M. S. Y. KHAN,* CH. I. Z. KHAN and S. U. KHAN

Department of Medicinal Chemistry,
Institute of History of Medicine & Medical Research,
Hamdard Nagar, New Delhi-110 062

Manuscript received 30 January 1984, revised 26 December 1984, accepted 30 April 1985

R = Ph, C₆H₄Me-*p*, C₆H₄Cl-*p*, C₆H₄Br-*p*, C₆H₄OMe-*p*, C₆H₄OEt-*p*, 2-Py;
R' = H, *p*-OMe, *p*-OEt, *p*-Br, *p*-Cl, *o*-Me, *m*-Me, *p*-Me.

OXIDATION of phloracetophenone dimethyl ether (1) was reported earlier¹ to yield 5,5'-linked dimer 2. The proof for its linkage was furnished by its conversion to hexa-*O*-methyl-6,6'-biapi-genin^{1,2}, differing from the common 8,8'-linked

cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether. We are now presenting another independent proof for the linkage and confirming the earlier assignment.

Chart A

The ketone dimer 2 was converted to bischrysin tetramethyl ether (4) by two methods, one involving the bischalcone (3) and the other through Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement of the bisester 5. The bischrysin tetramethyl ether obtained above can be *a priori* 6,6'' or 8,8''-linked. The tetramethyl ether was demethylated selectively at 5,5''-positions to give the dimethyl ether (7) which on tosylation gave 8. The ditosylate (8) on Raney nickel reduction yielded a mixture of two products which could not be separated. However, from a careful study of the nmr of the mixture, the products were identified as 7 and the deoxygenated product 9. Formation of 9 confirms the inter-flavonyl link at 6,6'' position and hence 5,5''-in the ketone dimer 2.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries in a paraffin bath and are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 , a drop of TFA was added where the solubility in CDCl_3 was

poor. Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained for all the compounds. Solvent systems used for tlc were toluene-ethyl formate-formic acid (5 : 4 : 1) and benzene-pyridine-formic acid (36 : 9 : 5). All the compounds were tlc pure.

Bischalcone 3: Bisphloroacetophenone tetramethyl ether (2; 3.0 g) was dissolved in ethanol (35.0 ml) and benzaldehyde (2.1 ml) was added to it. To the mixture was added dropwise while stirring, a solution of NaOH (7.5 g) in oxygen-free water (12.5 ml). A semi-solid orange mass separated out during the course of the reaction. The contents were left at room temperature for 12 h and then acidified with dilute HCl (1 : 1) to give an orange coloured solid, which was filtered, washed with water, then with NaHCO_3 solution (10%) and finally with water again. On crystallisation from methanol it gave the bischalcone (3) as orange crystals (2.5 g), m.p. 148°; gave a green colour with ferric chloride; δ 3.90 (12H, b, 4-OCH₃), 6.02 (2H, s, I-3', II-3') and 7.3-7.8 (m, 14H, remaining protons).

Tetra-O-methyl-6,6''-bischrysin (4): The bischalcone (3; 1.0 g) was dissolved in isoamyl alcohol (30.0 ml). Freshly sublimed SeO_2 (1.0 g) was added to it and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 48 h. The contents were then cooled to room temperature and filtered to remove the precipitated selenium. The filtrate was diluted with methanol and the solvent recovered on a boiling water bath under reduced pressure. The residue on crystallisation from methanol gave 4 as light yellow needles (800 mg), m.p. 255°; did not give any colour with ferric chloride and gave a pink colour with Mg and HCl; δ 3.98 (12H, s, 4-OCH₃), 6.52 (2H, s, I-8, II-8), 6.76 (2H, s, I-3, II-3), 7.50 (6H, m, I-3', 4', 5', II-3', 4', 5') and 7.90 (4H, m, I-2', 6', II-2', 6').

Bisester 5: Bisphloroacetophenone tetramethyl ether (2; 1.5 g) was dissolved in dry pyridine (9.0 ml) and freshly distilled benzoyl chloride (1.2 g) was added to it. The reaction flask was heated under anhydrous conditions at 100-110° for 3 h. The reaction mixture after cooling was poured into dilute HCl. A solid separated out which was filtered, washed with water, then with NaHCO_3 solution (10%) and finally with water. On crystallisation from methanol it gave 5 (1.0 g), m.p. 185°; δ 2.62 (6H, s, 2-COCH₃), 3.96, 4.0 (6H each, s, 4-OCH₃), 6.54 (2H, s, I-3, II-3), 7.6 and 8.15 (10H, m, 2C₆H₄).

Bis- β -diketone 6: The bisester (5; 1.0 g) was dissolved in dry pyridine (8.0 ml) and powdered KOH (1.0 g) was added to it. The reaction mixture was shaken for 3 h with occasional warming when it turned viscous. The contents were then diluted with ice-cold water and the cooled aqueous solution was poured into dilute HCl. A yellow precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol to give fine silky needles (800 mg), m.p. 160°; gave a green colour with ferric chloride; δ 3.42, 3.82, 3.88, 3.90 (12H, s, 4-OCH₃), the last two arising from enol form), 4.44 (s, -CH,

of the keto form); 7.20 (2H, s, I-3, II-3), 7.45 and 7.90 (10H, m, $2C_6H_8$).

Tetra-O-methyl, 6-6"-bischrysin (4): To a solution of the bis- β -diketone (6; 600 mg) in glacial acetic acid (20.0 ml) was added freshly fused sodium acetate (2.5 g) and the contents were heated on an oil bath for 4 h at 150-160°. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and diluted with water. A precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol as light yellow needles, 4 (300 mg), m.p. 254°. It was identical with the sample obtained above through bischalcone.

Selective demethylation of 4 to 7: Bischrysin tetramethyl ether (4; 1.0 g) was dissolved in dry CH_2Cl_2 (45.0 ml) and anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (600 mg) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a heating mantle for 30 h. The contents were then cooled to room temperature and diluted with water (500 ml). Dilute HCl (1:1) was added to acidify it. The solution was warmed on a water bath for 1 h and a yellow solid obtained was filtered, washed and dried. On crystallisation from methanol it gave bischrysin dimethyl ether, 7 (500 mg), m.p. 234°; gave a green colour with ferric chloride; δ (with one drop of TFA) 4.0 (6H, s, 2-OCH₃), 6.50 (2H, s, I-8, II-8), 7.0 (2H, s, I-3, II-3), 7.5 and 7.95 (10H, m, $2C_6H_8$).

Methylation of dimethyl bischrysin 7 to 4: The dimethyl bischrysin (7; 100 mg) was dissolved in dry acetone (50.0 ml), and dimethyl sulphate (1.0 ml) and fused K_2CO_3 (4.0 g) were added to it. The contents were refluxed for 30 h under anhydrous conditions and then worked up to give a compound, m.p. 254°, which was identical in all respects with 4.

Ditosylate 8: The dimethyl bischrysin (7; 200 mg) was dissolved in dry acetone (80.0 ml), and freshly crystallised tosyl chloride (220 mg) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.0 g) were added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 40 h and then after cooling to room temperature the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. To the residue was added cold water when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol as silky needles, 8 (100 mg), m.p. 246°. It did not give any colour with ferric chloride. Nmr could not be recorded due to solubility reasons.

Raney nickel reduction of 8: The ditosylate (8; 360 mg) was dissolved in dioxane (20.0 ml) and freshly prepared Raney nickel catalyst (360 mg) was added to it while stirring. Purified hydrogen gas was bubbled through the solution rapidly in the initial stages and later as a steady stream for 10 h. After completion of the reaction the catalyst was filtered off and dioxane was removed from the filtrate by distilling under reduced pressure. The residue was crystallised from methanol to give a light yellow compound (30 mg), m.p. 220-25°; gave a green colour with ferric chloride; tlc examination showed it to be a mixture of two compounds;

under uv light one spot showed a dull brown fluorescence and the other a blue fluorescence; δ 3.85 (6H, s, —OCH₃ of 7), 3.95 (6H, s, —OCH₃ of 9), 6.35 (2H, s, I-8, II-8 of 7), 6.40 (2H, s, I-8, II-8 of 9), 6.65 (2H, s, I-8, II-3 of 9), 6.70 (2H, s, I-3 II-3 of 7), 7.45, 7.85 (m, $2C_6H_8$ of both 7 and 9 and I-5, II-5 of 9).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Hakim Abdul Hameed Sahib, President, I.H.M.M.R., New Delhi, for facilities and award of a fellowship to one of them (Ch. I. Z. K.). The authors are also thankful to Dr. M. R. Parthasarathy for his valuable help throughout these studies, and to Dr. M. Ilyas and Prof. W. Rahman for their keen interest.

References

1. M. R. PARTHASARATHY, K. R. RANGANATHAN and D. K. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 942.
2. M. S. Y. KHAN, S. U. KHAN, CH. I. Z. KHAN and M. R. PARTHASARATHY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.

Chemical Investigation of *Bauhinia vahlii* Linn. (Leguminosae)

SARWAT SULTANA, M. ILYAS*, MOHAMMED KAMIL
and
W. A. SHAIDA

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 19 March 1984, accepted 30 April 1985

A survey of literature revealed the presence of monoflavonoids and their glycosides in different species of *Bauhinia*¹⁻³. Since no work appeared to have been done on *Bauhinia vahlii* so far, this was subjected to systematic investigations.

Leaves of *Bauhinia vahlii* were found to contain betulinic acid, campesterol, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, quercetin, quercetin-3-glucoside, kaempferol, agathisflavone and its derivatives. The presence of biflavonoids is being reported here for the first time in *Bauhinia* species.

Experimental

The dried and powdered leaves (2 kg) were extracted with acetone. The total acetone extract was concentrated and passed through silica-gel column. The column was eluted with solvents of increasing polarity: petrol, benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1, 8:2, 7:3, 1:1), ethyl acetate and acetone. The benzene and benzene-ethyl acetate fractions in first three ratios were mixed and refractionated over silica column. Elution with benzene-chloroform (1:1, v/v) gave a white crystalline solid, m.p. 122-28°. Gc-ms analysis of the